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USE OF TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS: AUDIO-VISUAL AND COMPUTER AIDED INSTRUCTION IN TEACHING AT SCHOOL LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

In the present day society 'technological innovation' is the key word. Educators have been impressively using technological innovations in the field of education. There is a section of educators who believe that 'all media suits all content areas', but at the same time there are many who believe that each technology can not be used with same potential for teaching all content areas. To test this, investigators have taken two supplementary modes of teaching like audio-visual programme and computer aided instruction (CAI) in teaching science at school level. An experimental study was conducted to compare achievement scores of samples before and after teaching within and among these two groups. The results are analysed based on the data obtained. The results indicate that both the methods of teaching are effective in teaching science at secondary level. However, from the results it seems that the CAI package results in superior achievement of students. Hence, there is an urgent need to have more number of studies in these areas so that the potential, of technology can be used to the requirement of teaching-learning in schools.

Key words: Audio-visual programme, Computer Aided Instructional Package

INTRODUCTION

Education is an important challenge for proper child rearing after food. The government of India has spent lot of money to meet this challenge and reach the grass root level stakeholders. Still satisfactory and balanced provisions of education have not been achieved. The engineers, doctors, managers, bureaucrats, astronauts etc. present shining side of educated society, but on the contrary some of the school dropouts go to menial works in the society and show not very shining picture of our country in general and education in particular.

What ways can be adopted to bridge the gap between these two sections of the student community? It is believed that the technology can bridge the gap. All sections of the students whether bright or average like technological equipments. The lack of quality teachers and teaching can also be overcome by the use of these teaching aids. It is a known fact that technology if utilized properly does not discriminate among people of different castes, creeds, geographical locations, languages etc. Quality programmes can help both teachers and taught alike and can go to the geographical length and breadth of the country. These programmes also help guiding students in personal capacity and can become supplementary to classroom teaching. Hence, it is the need of the hour to test whether the technologies like audio-visual and computers aided instruction are useful in teaching at secondary level. There is also a need to find out the most suitable technology for students at secondary level.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To prepare the Audio-visual and CAI package in science subject for 10th

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standard.

2. To impart the lesson through Audio-visual and CAI package
3. To compare the effectiveness of teaching between audio-visual method and CAI mode.

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of Experimental-1 and Experimental-2 group for pre test-1 of the unit solar energy-1.
2. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of Experimental-1 and Experimental-2 group for post test-1 of the unit solar energy-1.
3. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of Experimental-1 and Experimental-2 group for pre test-2 of the unit solar energy-2.
4. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of Experimental-1 and Experimental-2 group for post test-2 of the unit solar energy-2.
5. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of Experimental-1 for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-1.
6. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of Experimental-1 group for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-2.
7. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of Experimental-2 group for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-1.
8. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of Experimental-2 group for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-2.

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

The *SPM* was administered on the whole class to identify average intelligence of students. The students identified were randomly assigned to two groups namely experimental-1 and experimental-2 groups, which were treated with the audio-visual and CAI packages respectively. Before, giving the treatment a pre test was conducted to know the previous knowledge of students for the unit solar energy-1. After, the treatment the students were again tested for their achievement through a post test. The same process of pre test, treatment and post test was also followed for the solar energy-2 unit.

SAMPLING

The purposive random sampling method was adopted for finalizing sample. Before finalizing the sample population, the investigators conducted *SPM* test on the whole class. The students whose scores on this test were falling under average category were selected; each group consisted of 30 students and was randomly assigned to two groups. The total sample size was 60.

Variables of the study

Control Variable: The intelligence of the students.

Independent Variable: The methods of teaching namely Audio-visual programme and CAI package

Dependent Variable: The academic achievement of the students

Tools of the study

1. SPM test: The Standard Progressive Matrices (SPM) test developed by Raven was administered on the students to know their intelligence.
2. Science text book: The tenth standard science text book of Karnataka was selected as the basis for the content. Solar Energy unit was identified from the text book for development of the tools of the study.
3. Audio-visual programme: The investigators prepared an audio-visual programme for the study.
4. CAI Package: The computer aided instructional package was prepared for the study.
5. Achievement test: An achievement test was prepared for testing the students' performance before and after both the treatments for two units in the study.

TREATMENTS FOR STUDY

The present study consists of two groups having equated on similar intelligence scores. To know the difference between the groups they were subjected to different types of teaching strategies or methods. Based on the experimental conditions used these are classified as experimental-1 group and experimental-2 group.

(Experimental group -1)

In this method the investigators designed audio-visual package on selected i.e. solar energy-1 and solar energy-2 unit of 10th standard of science subject to attain same objectives of teaching as that of the other group in the study. It used audio-visual media and involved senses of listening and sight. The class teacher had to put on the DVD or VCR with the AV aid prepared by the investigator. The viewing was to be preceded by pre-viewing activities and followed by certain post-viewing activities, which were suggested in the package. In this mode of teaching the teacher was made to use video compact disc (VCD) player and television monitor with suitable output of audio for the classroom. Further, the teachers were given training to handle these equipments along with the conduct of pre-viewing and post-viewing activities specified in the concerned programme.

(Experimental group – 2)

In this method the investigators designed CAI package on selected unit *i.e.* solar energy-1 and solar energy-2 of 10th standard of science subject, which was same as that of previous group. The teachers monitored students progress, clarified their doubts regarding content and package. Teacher also arranged pre and post instructional activities. Based on the anticipated needs of programme implementation, teachers were given training on conduct of activities, use of apparatus like computer and CAI package content etc. The students were given freedom for learning at their own pace and freedom for asking doubts during learning.

DEVELOPMENT OF AUDIO-VISUAL PROGRAMME

The development of Audio-Visual Programme is an important aspect of present research. Hence, the investigators gave due importance for the development of this programme. The process involved in development is given in figure 1.

The first stage in development of audio-visual programme was planning. This stage included the work schedule preparation and listing of tasks to be performed in development of audio-visual programme. This was followed by script writing, in which investigators wrote the academic script. After writing of this script, investigators held discussions with producers and media experts and converted this academic script to camera ready script. The camera script was vetted from different dimensions like content, language, dialogue and its flow, camera positions, background in shooting etc. Subsequently, required modifications were made in the camera scripts. This stage paved way for identification of persons for playing role of appropriate characters. For this, investigators interacted with school children and identified few potential students based on their communication capabilities and suitability of appearance for programme requirement. These students or designated characters practiced and rehearsed for the programme. A dry run was held in front of the camera persons and producers, before actual shooting of the programme. The suggestions obtained from these media experts were learnt and practiced before the actual recording of programme. The recording stage was followed by editing of programme. In the editing stage the media experts removed unnecessary pauses, repetitions and added pictures, video clippings, animations relevant to the content at appropriate places. The programmers, thus developed were subjected to tryout in schools and feedback was obtained from students and teachers. This feedback was incorporated in final editing and ultimately programmers were thus made error free.

DEVELOPMENT OF CAI PACKAGE

The development of CAI package is a long process and is an important aspect of present research. Hence, the investigators gave due importance for development of CAI packages. The stages involved in the development and standardization of package are shown in a flow chart in figure 2.

The programme planning was the first stage, where in the investigators decided about the content, format of preparation of package, style of teaching, physical and financial requirements etc. This was carried forward with design of a CAI programme based on

requirements of the stakeholders. The CAI has four style of presentation and the investigators restricted for use of tutorial and drill and practice modes of teaching at secondary school level children in this study. The investigators then referred the material and planned outline of script and wrote the academic script of CAI programme. This was followed by consultations with software experts, who helped in finalization of CAI script based on media requirements. The programmers or software experts were then asked to prepare CAI packages. At this stage the content and context specific pictures, animations, questions and feedbacks were integrated properly. Care was taken that the objectives of the programme remained prime concern. The media and content experts reviewed the programmers, edited and incorporated important aspects at appropriate places. The programme, thus developed was subjected to try-out in schools. The programmers were tested for their effectiveness with regard to software, type or format of CAI and planning aspects. The errors free programmers were sent for final implementation in the schools. Based on defects the programmers were sent to correction at appropriate stages as shown in the flow chart in figure 1 till quality programme was prepared. The particulars of the software so developed are given in subsequent section.

DETAILS OF SOFTWARE

Name: Computer Aided Instruction

Subject: Science

Level: Secondary School

Hardware requirement: Computer

Monitor (VDU): Monitor of the Computer

User Interface: Keyboard and Mouse

Special Features: user friendly package

Purpose: In the present situation of the secondary education system it is very essential to use computer as an aid of teaching. This will definitely change the status of education and bring the quality education.

VALIDITY OF THE PROGRAMME:

Content validity: The content selected for the programme was based on the objectives set for the programme. All the intended points were covered and properly presented in the programme. This shows that the content is valid.

Concurrent validity: The programme content was based on the existing syllabus of SSLC prevailing in Karnataka. This was appropriate for present day needs. Hence it is concurrent.

Construct Validity: The programme was constructed based on learning theories. Interactivity was also in built into it. Hence, it had construct validity.

Face validity: The programme was a representative of individualized instruction of a lesson. Hence, it had face validity.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

The investigators used statistical techniques like mean, standard deviation and t-value.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

H1: There is no significant difference between the scores of Experimental Group - 1 and Experimental Group - 2 for pre test 1 of Solar Energy 1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 1,

Table 1, showing t-value between Experimental-1 and Experimental group - 2 for pre-test-1

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Exptl1	30	29	4.533	1.01	0.29	1.23
Exptl2	30	29	4.166	1.29		

* not significant

From table 1, it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 1.23 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.756. The table value of 't' is greater than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H1 is accepted. Hence, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the means of Experimental Group -1 and Experimental Group - 2 for pre test score for the unit Solar Energy 1.

This means that both the groups under study, which are being taught through audio-visual and CAI possesses no difference with regard to their pre test scores on the unit on Solar Energy-1.

H2: There is no significant difference between the scores of Experimental Group - 1 and Experimental Group - 2 for post test 1 of solar energy 1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 2,

Table 2, showing t-value between Experimental Group - 1 and Experimental Group - 2 for post-test 1

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Exptl1	30	29	16.4	1.32	0.32	21.35
Exptl2	30	29	23.16	1.11		

* Significant

From table 2, it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 21.35 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.756. The table value of 't' is less than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H2 is rejected. Hence, it indicates that there is significant difference between the means of Experimental Group - 1 and Experimental Group - 2 on post test score on Solar Energy1. After observing the means of both the group it can be drawn that the mean score is in favour of Experimental Group - 2. That is after treatment the achievement of Experimental Group - 2 group is better than Experimental Group - 1.

This means that group which was taught unit Solar Energy-1 through CAI method achieved more than that of the group taught by Audio-Visual Programme.

H3: There is no significant difference between the scores of Experimental Group - 1 and Experimental Group - 2 group for pre test 2 of Solar Energy 2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 3,

Table 3, showing t-value between Experimental Group - 1 and Experimental Group - 2 group for pre-test 2

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Exptl1	30	29	4.17	1.09	0.28	0.24
Exptl2	30	29	4.23	1.07		

* not significant

From table 3, it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 0.24 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.756. The table value of 't' is greater than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H3 is accepted. Hence, it indicates that there is no significant difference between the means of Experimental-1 and Experimental-2 group.

This means that both the groups under study, which are being taught through Audio-Visual and CAI possesses no difference with regard to their pre test scores on the unit on Solar Energy-2.

H4: There is no significant difference between the scores of Experimental Group - 1 and Experimental Group - 2 for post test 2 of Solar Energy 2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 4,

Table 4 showing t-value between Experimental Group - 1 and Experimental Group - 2 group for post-test 2 in the unit solar energy 2

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Exptl1	30	29	16.03	1.52	0.34	12.45
Exptl2	30	29	20.33	1.12		

* Significant

The table 4 indicates that the calculated value of 't' is 12.45 and the table value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The table value of 't' is less than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H4 is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference between means of Experimental Group - 1 and Experimental Group - 2 for post test 2 of Solar Energy 2. Looking at the means it can be inferred that the mean score is in favour of Experimental Group - 2. That means after treatment the achievement of Experimental Group - 2 is better than Experimental Group - 1.

This means that group which was taught unit solar energy-2 through CAI method achieved more than that of the group taught by audio-visual programme.

H5: There is no significant difference between mean score of pre-test and post-test of Experimental Group - 1 for the unit Solar Energy 1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 5,

Table 5, showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Experimental Group -1 for Solar Energy1

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Pre test	30	29	4.53	1.01	0.31	38.97
Post test	30	29	16.4	1.33		

* Significant

From table 5, the calculated value is 38.97 and table value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The calculate values is more than the table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test scores of Experimental Group - 1 in Solar Energy 1. The means of both the scores indicates that Experimental Group - 1 students perform well after teaching.

This means that group which was taught unit solar energy-1 through audio-visual programme achieved more after treatment.

H6: There is no significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental-1group for the solar energy 2 unit.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 6,

Table 6, showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Experimental-1group for solar energy2

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Pre test	30	29	4.16	1.09	0.34	34.80
Post test	30	29	16.03	1.52		

* Significant

From table 6, the calculated value is 34.80 and table value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The calculate values is more than the table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental Group - 1 in Solar Energy 2 unit. The means of both the scores indicates that Experimental-1group students perform very well after teaching unit solar energy 2.

This means that group which was taught unit Solar Energy-2 through Audio-Visual Programme achieved more after treatment.

H7: There is no significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental-2 group for the Solar Energy 1 unit.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 7,

Table 7, showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Experimental Group -2 for Solar Energy1

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Pre test	30	29	4.16	1.29	0.31	61.03
Post test	30	29	23.16	1.12		

* Significant

From table 7, the calculated value is 61.035 and table value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The calculate values is more than the table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental Group - 2 for Solar Energy 1 unit. The means of both the scores indicates that Experimental Group - 2 group students perform very well after treatment or teaching through Audio-Visual Programme.

This means that group which was taught unit solar energy-1 through CAI package achieved more after treatment.

H8: There is no significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental Group - 2 for the Solar Energy 2 unit.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 8,

Table 8, showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Experimental Group -2 for Solar Energy 2

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Pre test	30	29	4.23	1.07	0.63	25.77
Post test	30	29	20.33	3.25		

* Significant

From table 8, the calculated value is 25.77 and table value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The calculate values is more than the table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental Group - 2 for Solar Energy 2 unit. The means of both the scores indicates that Experimental Group - 2 students perform very well after treatment or teaching through Audio-Visual Programme.

This means that group which was taught unit Solar Energy-2 through CAI package achieved more after treatment.

MAJOR FINDINGS

1. Both the groups under study, which were taught through Audio-Visual and CAI possessed no difference with regard to their pre test scores on the unit on Solar Energy-1.

2. The group which was taught unit Solar Energy-1 through CAI method achieved more than that of the group taught by Audio-Visual Programme.
3. Both the groups under study, which were taught through Audio-Visual and CAI possessed no difference with regard to their pre test scores on the unit on Solar Energy-2.
4. The group which was taught unit Solar Energy-2 through CAI method achieved more than that of the group taught by Audio-Visual Programme.
5. The group which was taught unit Solar Energy-1 through Audio-Visual Programme achieved more after treatment.
6. The group which was taught unit Solar Energy-2 through Audio-Visual Programme achieved more after treatment.
7. The group which was taught unit Solar Energy-1 through CAI package achieved more after treatment.
8. The group which was taught unit Solar Energy-2 through CAI package achieved more after treatment.

CONCLUSION

Computers are useful in different fields of life including education. Teachers access information through computers and use it for presentation of content to the classroom. There are various commercially available educational resources, which could be used for teaching. The teachers' role changes while making the use of these packages. It is based on the requirement of students that teachers provide the content. The innovativeness, colorfulness, preparation format and individualized pattern of teaching help the learner better. The teacher can make use of simple packages like word, excel, power point, flash for teaching their content areas. The present study has demonstrated that the computer technology can be effectively used for teaching in the classroom.

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